

DEVELOPMENT TECHNOLOGY FOR PRE-SCHOOL CHILDREN IN SURROUNDING KNOWLEDGE

Rahmonkulova Khalida Bosimovna

teacher, Jizzakh State Pedagogical University,
Department of Preschool Education Methodology

Annotation: In this article, the technology of speech development in preschool children's knowledge of surroundings,

It is thought that by studying the theoretical and practical recommendations of Western and Eastern speakers in the formation of children's speech, it will be effective in the education system by conveying their speech-related thoughts and recommendations to the students.

Key words: Rhetoric, strategy, school of mothers, mind and speech, Address, "New Uzbekistan", "Third Renaissance".

In educational institutions, in particular, formation of communicative competences of students of pre-school educational institutions, development of speech skills is one of the important issues of competent and person-oriented educational technologies. Communicative competences are the product of speech activities related to the thorough mastering of academic subjects, entering into social relations, reaching a critical and non-standard way of thinking, expressing one's opinion clearly and comprehensibly, so it is necessary to pay great attention to the formation and development of these competencies in students from the early stages of preschool education and general education schools. necessary, and this is also one of the most important conditions for the formation of personal competencies in students.

The formation and development of children's speech has been one of the main problems of pedagogy. In fact, the formation of children's speech depends on several factors, and their analysis provides a correct approach to the solution of this problem.

These factors include the environment in the family and educational institution, the child's mental state, capabilities, physical health, activity, moral and aesthetic qualities. Scientific-theoretical justification of the place of rich folklore examples in the development of children's speech, as well as the possibilities of mental and physiological influence of a number of genres in folk art is one of the current issues of such sciences as linguistics, literary studies, folklore studies, psychology and pedagogy. The fact that the subject takes place at the intersection of several disciplines indicates that it is a comprehensive scientific problem.

The analysis and description of the conducted scientific work and research provides an opportunity to determine the scientific basis and research level of improving the speech of children of primary school age.

Research on the development of children's speech of primary school age began in our country in the 50s of the last century. A. V. Nikolskaya, one of the first scientists to study the field of primary education, researches the problem in the context of teaching the Russian language to children of the local nationality. As a result of experimental studies conducted by A.V. Nikolskaya (1958-60 years), teaching Russian oral speech to primary adult Uzbek children

the main content of the methodology is determined and its main issues are developed.

In the 70s of the 20th century, under the scientific guidance of A.V. Nikolskaya, E.M. Razbaeva's researches highlighted the role of folklore works in educating respect for the work of adults based on the works read to children of primary school age. In particular, in this study, the role of socially useful work in human development in young people through work and ritual songs, the fact that work is an excellent educational tool, the formation of fair treatment to others based on the use of Uzbek folklore (folk tales, games) were analyzed through examples of Uzbek folklore.

These studies show the role of folklore in the spiritual development of a person, especially in the upbringing of children. In fact, "Folklore is the beginning, root of all art, therefore, it has harmony with many other arts, and therefore, it is a special type of art, distinguished by its uniqueness, which is not like any other. This field includes imagination related to music, dance, crafts, visual, artistic and other arts. In other words, oral creativity is a creative process that expresses the past, present and future of the nation and is closely related to its destiny. That is why our scholars called it folk literature. In order to know what kind of people a nation is, it is necessary to look at its folklore first. The saying that the beginning of any art is in folklore did not appear today. It is the result of long-term life observation, scientific experience. In fact, the appearance of visual arts, handicrafts, music, dance, speech and other types of art directly goes back to folk oral creativity, the first imaginations and beliefs of the people.

Undoubtedly, folklore is a form of speech art with great potential and rich values in the education of children, especially in the development of their speech. In particular, the fact that his genres such as fairy tales, legends, narratives, quick sayings, riddles, and proverbs are of great importance in educating students' worldview, imagination, thinking abilities, memory, spirit, and speech is reflected in the uniqueness and internal capabilities of these genres.

Language, speech and thinking are very important in the process of human development. At this point, we consider it appropriate to dwell a little on the linguistic analysis of these concepts.

Language is closely related to consciousness and thinking. These two concepts complement each other and one cannot exist without the other. The process of thinking takes place in our mind in the form of language elements. Words and other linguistic elements appear as concepts in the mind as means of thinking. This process cannot take place without language elements. Therefore, language is closely related to consciousness and thinking.

Speech is a phenomenon related to language, and its improvement depends on the availability of lexical units in the language from the quick memory of a person and his ability to quickly use them in the speech process. Without increasing a person's vocabulary

speaking skills cannot be developed. Also, feeling the stylistic specificity of lexical units and their specific meanings, based on experience and natural intuition, increases the ability of a person to use words appropriately. These are linguo-psychological skills that are formed through attention to words, artistic reading, various social relations, and can be influenced by internal and external factors.

The main stage of acquiring speech corresponds to the period of primary education, and then it has a regular development. Based on this, currently, a lot of attention is being paid to the separate study of the stages of speech development. Children's speech researchers of primary school age E.I. Tikheeva, E.A. Flerina, A.M. Leushina, L.A. Penevskaya and others, the specific features of the development of children's oral speech and acquisition of storytelling skills, with a dialogic form of speech and monologic interrelationships, differences and similarities in speech expression, factors forming fluent speech were studied. Also, practical aspects of the development of children's speech by these researchers, in particular, the classification of children's stories, the role of the process of reading (listening) to the story in the formation of speech, describing the surrounding objects, narrating literary works, telling stories based on pictures, giving examples from personal and collective experience, such factors as creative storytelling are described.

The development of children's speech of primary school age is based on the practical work carried out in this direction in preschool educational institutions. Therefore, it is appropriate to ensure the integration of work on the formation and development of speech in preschool and primary education, to reconsider the issues of coherence and continuity in the programs. In this regard, it is appropriate to pay attention to the issue of speech formation in preschool education: the ability to

express thoughts, related speech skills, and in primary education, it is appropriate to pay attention to the issue of its development; in primary education, it is possible to create a story based on a picture, to retell an artistic text, and to pay attention to the grammatical nature of language elements.

Theoretical and practical research on the formation and development of children's speech is the reason for increasing the incentive to improve speech activity. An effective communication process is decided when speech activity is integrated with speech actions. This approach occupies a central place in the theoretical views of Russian researchers on the development of children's speech activity. It has been proven that appropriate and effective use of verbal and non-verbal forms of communication increases the effectiveness of speech.

The issue of education and training occupies a special place in the creative work of one of the Uzbek enlighteners, Abdulla Avloni. As a scientist and teacher, poet and writer, theater leader and director, he sees the development of the Motherland in the education of the children of the local people, and in this way he carries out serious works of practical importance. In particular, he pays special attention to the problem of educating Uzbek girls and establishing special schools for them. During his career, Avloni wrote and published textbooks such as "Adabiyot" (Books I-IIIV), "First Teacher" ("First Teacher"), "Second Teacher" ("Second Teacher"), "Turkiy Gulistan", "Maktab Gulistan". .

Abdulla Awlani puts the problem of learning in the first place in his works. Among other things, he says: "As a result, our whole life, health, happiness, wealth, life, effort, enthusiasm, world and hereafter are connected with knowledge. That's why we should not miss the opportunity to learn and learn, and try our best to get rid of ignorance, which is the enemy of our body.

The reformation of the teaching and learning method, the establishment of new schools, the introduction of modern knowledge to students, the introduction of

Eastern and Western languages into the educational practice are connected with the name of Abdulla Avloni.

Abdulla Avloni, realizing that the role of fiction in the education of young people is incomparable, brings examples of folk oral creativity and written literature in his textbooks in order to justify a certain form of education.

Russian literature and culture play an important role in the formation of Abdulla Avloni's worldview. He had great respect for the creative heritage of A.S. Pushkin, L.N. Tolstoy, M. Gorky and highly appreciated the pedagogical heritage of K. D. Ushinsky. In Avloni's pedagogical views, the development of children's speech activity is considered in connection with fiction. As a pedagogue, he sees the linguistic and communicative possibilities of fiction as the main factor in children's spiritual maturity, in particular, in the development of their speech. Two aspects of the short stories given in Avloni's original textbooks can be distinguished:

1) instructive conclusions in the stories are an educational aspect related to broadening the students' outlook, enriching their conclusions about life, developing their thinking;

2) an educational aspect related to the speech skills acquired during the reading of stories.

Therefore, in his concept of education and upbringing, Abdulla Avloni paid attention to the issue of developing children's speech skills, and considered fiction as the main tool for their development.

In general, the issue of children's speech development has been attracting the attention of the scientific community for a long time as a comprehensive and multifactorial pedagogical problem. In them, the problem is studied from different aspects. Especially in this regard, the services of Russian pedagogic scientists are great, and there are still many studies that need to be carried out by local researchers. Undoubtedly, researching the issue of children's speech development from different angles has not only scientific, but also practical significance.

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